

EFFECT OF DIGITALISATION- A STUDY OF SELECT RURAL AND URBAN HOUSEHOLDS IN KERALA

Abstract

Digital India comprises of various initiatives under the single programme each targeted to prepare India for becoming a knowledge economy and for bringing good governance to citizens through synchronized and co-ordinated engagement of the entire Government. The paper aims to evaluate the effectiveness of digitalisation among the household in Kerala and also to compare the perception of households in urban area and rural area. A sample of hundred was selected using convenient sampling method which include fifty from urban area and fifty from rural area. The perceptions of households in rural and urban area are almost same in all these aspects. In rural area people still stick on offline method for the payment of the bills but it is comparatively better in urban area. It was found that the digitalisation is effective but the perception of households in urban and rural area with regard to the level of effectiveness is different.

Key words: Digital payments, Effectiveness of digitalisation, Internet connections

Introduction

The term 'Digital Economy' was coined in Don Tapscott's 1995 book *The Digital Economy: Promise and Peril in the Age of Networked Intelligence*. The *Digital Economy* was among the first books to consider how the Internet would change the way we did business. According to Thomas Mesenbourg (2001), three main components of the - 'Digital Economy' concept can be identified: e-business infrastructure (hardware, software, telecoms, networks, human capital, etc.), e-business (how business is conducted, any process that an organization conducts over computer-mediated networks) and e-commerce (transfer

of goods, for example when a book is sold online). The concept of Digital India was launched in the year 2015 with the objective of connecting the rural areas with high speed internet network and improving digital literacy. The vision of Digital India programme is inclusive growth in areas of electronic services, products, manufacturing and job opportunities etc. and it is centered on three key areas: Digital Infrastructure as a Utility to Every Citizen, Governance & Services on Demand and Digital Empowerment of Citizens.

Research Problem

The aim of government of India is to convert our economy into a digital economy within 5 or 6 years. The government is taking various measures to promote cashless transaction in the country. Within three years itself, the government converted many sectors into digital sector and some others are in the process of digitalisation. This research work would like to evaluate the effect of digitalisation among the households in the rural and urban area of Kerala. The following research questions are relevant in this context.

- How far the concept of Digital India is effective?
- Are the customers doing the transactions digitally?
- Do they make the payment of electricity, water bills etc. digitally, or they still stick on the traditional method?
- Are they using debit/credit card for payment or still doing cash payment?
- Is there any difference in the attitude of customers towards digitalisation in urban area and rural area?

Review of Literature

Review of literature helps to gain background knowledge of the research topics and to identify the concept relating to it. Many studies are conducted with regard to cashless economy; some of them are as follows:

Vaibhav Shahaji & Jyoti Mishra (2017) conducted a study on cashless India. The main aim of the study was to identify the merit and demerits of converting India into cashless India. Many developed countries had already been converted into cashless economy, but India is still only in a process. The government should take some measures to make the customers aware about cashless transactions. They are afraid of doing this, so the government should introduce some incentives to attract the customers towards cashless transactions and also through banks or other intermediaries government should take some measures to familiarize the customers about the technology. The main drawback faced by the country is with regard to the speed of internet connection.

V.Kokila & R.Ushadevi (2017) tried to identify the attitude of customers towards cashless transaction. The study was limited to puduchery. The researcher aims to identify the customer's awareness on cashless transaction and the changes that happened in Puduchery during the period of demonetisation. The study also covers the policies and reforms introduced by the government during the period of demonetisation to promote digital payments.

Deepika Kumari (2016) tried to identify the challenges faced by the people during the period of demonetisation and about the measures taken by the government to face the situation. It also covered the methods and applications adopted by the government to promote digitalisation. The advertisement was one of the important methods adopted by government to promote cashless transaction.

Objectives of the Study

- To analyze the perception of households towards digitalised transaction.
- To compare the attitude of households in urban and rural area towards digitalisation.

Hypotheses

- Ho: There is no significant difference in the attitude of households towards the effectiveness of digitalisation with regard to location
- Ho: There is no significant difference in the method used for payment with regard to location.
- Ho: There is no significant difference in the attitude of households in urban and rural area with regard to positives of digitalisation
- Ho: There is no significant difference in the attitude of people towards reasons for not doing Digital transactions with regard to location.

Scope & Significance of the study

In order to identify how far the concept of the digital economy is effective among the households there is a need to conduct a study. The paper aims to study the digitalisation in Kerala. It also tried to identify the perception of households towards digitalisation and also to compare the attitude of rural and urban respondents towards digitalisation.

Research Methodology and Data Base

The study is designed as a descriptive one based on both primary data and secondary data. The secondary data, necessary for the study was collected from various sources: journals, magazines and website. Since most of the information necessary to fulfil the objectives of the study was not available from secondary data, the study is mainly based on primary data collected through a sample survey using structured questionnaire.

Sample Design

A sample of 100 was chosen from among the households in Kerala. For the purpose of collecting the data entire state was divided into two; based on the locality i.e. rural area and urban area. 50 samples were drawn from rural area and other 50 sample was drawn from urban area using convenient sampling method. The total number of respondents includes households from different age group, income level and gender.

Tools used for Data Collection

Field survey was conducted to collect primary data from the households. A well structured questionnaire was developed to collect data from the respondents.

Tools for Data Analysis

For the purpose of data analysis various statistical tools and mathematical techniques were used such as:

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi square test
- Independent sample t test

Variables used for the Study

- Bill payment
- Card payment
- Online purchase
- Speed of internet
- Pay-tm/Free-charge

Limitations of the Study

As in the case of almost all social science research, this study is also not free from certain inherent limitations as stated below:

1. The sample for the study comprised of hundred households, which includes fifty urban households and other fifty rural households, which is only a very small proportion of the entire population of households in Kerala. Therefore, research studies with much larger sample size would be required to ensure appropriate generalization of the findings of the study.
2. Convenient sampling method was adopted for selecting the sample. Hence, it may not be representative.
3. To evaluate the effectiveness of digitalisation on households only five selected variables was considered, rest were ignored.

Results and Discussion

The primary data collected through the questionnaire was analysed using percentage method, Chi-square and Independent t test. The results obtained are as follows:

Demographic Characteristics of the households

Equal number of household was selected from both the urban and rural area of Kerala. The following table reveals the demographic characteristics of the respondents.

Table 1 Summarised General Profile of the Respondents

	Demographic Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	38	38
	Female	62	62
	Total	100	100
Location	Urban	50	50
	Rural	50	50
	Total	100	100
Age group	Below 25	16	16
	25-35	36	36
	35-45	13	13
	45-55	21	21
	55&above	14	14
	Total	100	100
Annual Income	Below 50000	24	24
	50000-100000	21	21
	100000-150000	0	0
	150000-200000	19	19
	200000-250000	4	4
	250000-300000	6	6
	300000 & above	26	26
	Total	100	100

Source:Field Survey

The above table shows the demographic profile of the sample respondents. 62% of the respondents were Female and 38% male. Majority of the respondents (36%) belongs to the age group of 25-35. 26% of the respondents have annual income above 300000, 24% have below 50000 and 21% have between 50000 and 100000.

Effectiveness of digitalisation

The government of India decided to convert India into ‘Digital India’. As a part of this move, the government is digitalising all the transactions. Even then how many of the households are doing the transactions digitally. In order to identify the respondent’s opinion about the effectiveness of digital transaction, the following data was collected.

Table 2 Effectiveness of digital transactions

Digital transactions	Frequency	Per cent
Effective	69	69
Not so effective	19	19
Not effective	12	12
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey

As per the above table, majority of the respondents (69%) opined that digitalisation is effective, 19% opined that it is not so effective and only 12% opined that it is not effective.

Effectiveness of digitalisation and location

For analyzing the effectiveness of digitalisation on households from different locality, independent sample t test is used. The location of the respondents is categorized into two, namely urban and rural. In this respect a hypothesis was formulated.

- Ho: There is no significant difference in the attitude of people towards the effectiveness of digitalisation with regard to location

Table 3 Result of Independent Sample t-test on Effectiveness of Digitalisation and location

		T test for equality of Means				
		T	df	Sig.(2 tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
Effectiveness of digitalisation	Equal variance assumed	-2.807	98	0.006	-0.380	0.135
	Equal variance not assumed	-2.807	78.106	0.006	-0.380	0.135

Source: Field Survey

The calculated value (0.006) is less than 0.05 the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is significant difference in the attitude of people towards the effectiveness of digitalisation with regard to location.

Mode of payment

There are mainly two modes for payment i.e. online and offline. In the earlier period majority of the households were doing offline mode of payment. After introducing the concept of Digital India, is there any changes in the modes of payments preferred. The following table shows the respondents' opinion about the mode of payment commonly preferred.

Table 4 Mode of Payment

Mode of payment	Frequency	Per cent
Online	14	14
Offline	86	86
Total	100	100

Source: Field survey

The above table reveals that majority of the respondents (86%) prefer offline mode for payment. Only 14% prefer online mode for payment.

Method of payment and location

There are different methods for making payment while purchasing the products like cash, cards or other payment methods. In order to identify which is the most frequently used payment method and also to test any difference in the payment method preferred by the respondents according to the locality they belong, the following hypothesis was formulated.

- Ho: There is no significant difference in the method used for payment with regard to location.

Table 5 Result of Chi-Square on Method of payment and location

Methods of payment	Area		Total	Per cent
	Urban	Rural		
Debit card	20	18	38	38
Credit card	2	5	7	7
Cash	16	20	36	36
Other methods like pay-tm, Freecharge	3	1	4	4
All of the above	9	6	15	15
Total	50	50	100	100
P-value: 0.488, df:4				

Source: Field survey

The calculated value (0.488) is more than 0.05 the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference in the method used for payment with regard to location.

As per the above table majority of the respondents (38%) make payment using debit card and 36% makes cash payments. Only 4% is using other payment methods like paytm, freecharge etc.

Online Bill Payments

In the earlier period, people have to go the corresponding office for paying electricity, water, telephone bills etc. and also have to stand in the queue which takes a lot of time. But now the payment of the bills can be done online, no need of standing in the queue or going to the office. Only thing is that need an internet connection. It saves the time and energy. In order to identify whether the respondents make the payment of bills online or still they stick on the traditional methods of bill payment the following data was collected.

Table 6 Online Bill payment

Digital transactions	Urban		Rural		Total	
	Frequency	Per cent	Frequency	Per cent	Frequency	Per cent
Electricity bill	6	12	7	14	13	13
Water bill	2	4	0	0	2	2
Telephone bill	10	20	9	18	19	19
None of the above	14	28	26	52	40	40
All of the above	18	36	8	16	26	26
Total	50	100	50	100	100	100

Source: Field survey

As per the above table (40%) of the respondents still stick on the traditional methods of bill payment and only 26% of the respondents do all the bill payment digitally. While comparing the rural and urban respondents, 52% of rural respondents are using offline

method for bill payment but only 28% of the urban respondents use offline method. Majority of the urban respondents (36%) is doing all the bill payments online, 20% is doing only telephone bills,12% is doing only electricity bills and 4% is doing only water bills online while only 16% of the rural respondents do all the payments online.

Speed of Internet

For doing the transactions digitally there is a need of internet connection. Speed of internet is one of the important factor that influence the digital transaction because while doing the payment if the speed of internet connection is low it will take a lot of time to complete the process and sometimes it may exceed the time limit and the transaction will get cancelled. It will create a tension in the minds of the people and will be discouraged from doing digital transaction. In order to identify the respondent’s opinion about speed of internet connection in their locality the following data was collected.

Table 7 Speed of Internet connection in their locality

Speed of Internet	Rural		Urban		Total	
	Frequency	Per cent	Frequency	Per cent	Frequency	Per cent
High	5	10	10	20	15	15
Average	39	78	34	68	73	73
Low	6	12	6	12	12	12
Total	50	100	50	100	100	100

Source: Field Survey

As per the above table 73% of the respondents opined that the speed of internet is only average. 20% of the urban respondents opined that they have high speed internet connection but in rural area its only 10%. Majority of the respondents in urban area (68%) and rural area (78%) opined that speed of internet connection is only average.

Positives of Digital transactions

The concept of Digital India was introduced with a lot of positive moves. The government also take various measures to promote cashless transactions, by doing the transactions digitally will help save the time and energy. In order to identify the respondents view about positives of digital transaction the following data was collected

Table 8 Positives of Digital transactions

Positives of Digital transactions	Frequency	Per cent
Time Saving	36	36
More Convenient	24	24
Safe	4	4
Reduces the risk handling cash	17	17
None	2	2
All of the above	17	17
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey

As per the table 36% of the respondents opined that time saving are the main advantage of digital transaction. While 24% opined that it's more convenient. 17% opined that it helps to reduce the risk in handling cash and other 17% opined that it has all the positive mentioned above, 4% opined that its safe. It was quite interesting to note that only 2% opined that digital transaction doesn't have any positives.

Positives of Digitalisation and location

For analyzing the perception of households from different locality towards positives of digitalisation, independent sample t test is used. The location of the

respondents is categorized into two, namely urban and rural. In this respect a hypothesis was formulated.

- Ho: There is no significant difference in the attitude of households in urban and rural area with regard to positives of digitalisation

Table 9 Result of t-test on Positives of Digitalisation and location

		T test for equality of Means				
		T	Df	Sig.(2 tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
Positives of digitalisation	Equal variance assumed	0.322	98	.748	.120	.372
	Equal variance not assumed	0.322	97.978	.748	.120	.372

Source: Field survey

As the calculated value (0.748) is more than 0.05 the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference in the attitude of households in urban and rural area with regard to positives of digitalisation.

Reasons for not doing Digital transactions

Almost all the transactions can be done digitally and also the government is taking measures to promote cashless transactions. Still, a part the people are not doing the transactions digitally. The following table reveals the reason for not doing the transaction digitally.

Table 10 Reason for not doing digital transactions

Reasons for not doing Digital transactions	Frequency	Per cent
Afraid of fraudulent activities	22	22.0
No trust in the security of electronic payment methods	7	7.0
Prefer paying offline or in person	23	23.0
Slow internet access speed	10	10.0
Do not know how to use electronic payment methods	6	6.0
Not Applicable	32	32.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Field survey

As per the above table, 32% said that they always do digital transaction. But 23% said that they prefer paying offline or in person, 22% said that they are afraid of fraudulent activities, 10% said that slow internet access speed, 7% said that no trust in the security of electronic payment methods and 6% said that they do not know how to use electronic payment methods.

Reasons for not doing Digital transactions & location

For analyzing the attitude of households from different locality towards reasons for not doing Digital transactions, independent sample t test is used. The location of the respondents is categorised into two, namely urban and rural. In this respect a hypothesis was formulated.

Ho: There is no significant difference in the attitude of households towards reasons for not doing Digital transactions with regard to location.

Table 11 Result of t-test on Reasons for not doing Digital transactions and location

Independent Samples T test						
		T test for equality of Means				
		T	Df	Sig. (2 tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
Reasons for not doing Digital transactions	Equal variance assumed	0.293	98	0.770	0.140	0.478
	Equal variance not assumed	0.293	94.343	0.770	0.140	0.478

Source: Field survey

The calculated value (0.770) is more than 0.05 the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference in the attitude of households towards reasons for not doing Digital transactions with regard to location.

Findings

- Digitalisation is effective but the perception of households in rural and urban area is different.
- People prefer offline mode of payment than online. Even then they are making payments using debit cards as well.
- In rural area people still stick on the traditional methods for the payment of electricity, telephone and water bill but it's comparatively better in urban area.
- Speed of internet is only average in both rural and urban area.
- The main advantages of digital transactions are time saving and convenience. And the perception of rural area and urban area with regard to the positives are same.

- The main reason for not doing the transaction digitally are they are afraid of fraudulent activities, and they prefer paying offline or in person. And there is no difference in the perception of respondents in urban area and rural area with regard to the reason for not doing digital transaction.

Conclusion

For evaluating the effectiveness of digital transactions equal number of respondents were selected from both urban and rural area of Kerala State. The main advantages of digital transactions are time saving and more convenient. But still the customers prefer offline mode for doing the transactions as they are afraid of fraudulent activities, and they prefer payment in offline or in person. Even then they started using debit card for making payments while purchasing the goods but for the bill payments like electricity, water, telephone etc. they still stand in the queue and make payment. Eventhough the customers are not doing much digital transactions; they believe that digitalisation is effective. But the perception of people in urban and rural area with regard to effectiveness of digitalisation is different.

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